

Contributory factors and prevalent causes of medication errors among nurses in Cebu City

Joel B. Serad
Center for Research and Development
University of the Visayas
joelserad@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

The researcher determined the contributory factors and prevalent causes of medication errors among nurses in Cebu City. The increasing incidence of medication errors nowadays prompted the researcher to explore the different factors and causes of this healthcare concern. This is something of value since it served as a basis in formulating a plan of preventive measures. This study utilized a quantitative correlational research with a descriptive qualitative method. Basically, there were 100 nurses who participated in the study. These nurses were chosen based on a specified criteria and data collection was conducted on these participants who came from different tertiary public and private hospitals in Cebu City. With the help of SSPS, the findings of this study revealed that the topmost common contributory factors of medication error are high workload, stress and level of tiredness, communication problem, and working environment while topmost common prevalent causes are illegible physician's order, computing the wrong dose, and not identifying the right patient. Further, it revealed that generally the most of the items from the contributory factors and prevalent causes of medication errors do not have significant relationships with each other. This study was inspired by the Human Error theory by James Reason. It explained that mistakes or errors are human-nature. In this study, a proposed preventive measure was formulated to help combat the occurrence of medication errors. These measures include professional and systemic reforms. These reforms aimed to change not only the person but the whole system or organization, as well.

Keywords: *contributory factors, prevalent causes, medication errors, nurses, Cebu City, preventive measures*

I. INTRODUCTION

Medication errors continually rise in practice – just as when patients thought nurses could help them, it is when nurses intentionally or unintentionally put them at risk instead. According to the National Coordinating Council for Medication Error Reporting and Prevention (2009):

“Medication error is any preventable event that may cause or lead to inappropriate medication use or patient harm while the medication is in the control of the healthcare professional, the patient, or the consumer. Such events may be related to professional practice, health care products, procedures, and

systems, including prescribing; order communication; product labeling and nomenclature; compounding; dispensing; distribution; administration; education; monitoring; and use.”

Robert Naylor (2002) claimed that many people, including those in the health care professions, considered medication error commission as uniquely unpleasant subject and something that should not be discussed. Aside from involving additional human and financial costs to the patients, their families, and the healthcare systems (Glavin, 2010; The Medication Errors Panel, 2007; The Institute of Medicine Committee on the Quality of Health Care in America, 1999; Pinilla, Murillo, Carrasco & Humet, 2006; Naylor, 2002), it also induces demoralizing effects on the reputation (Cook & Hoas, 2009; Simpson & Knox, 2009; Interdisciplinary Conference, 2008; Naylor, 2002) that grounds severe damage to trust and confidence (Jacobs, 2004; Selbst, 2003; Naylor, 2002) among health care providers.

Medication errors can occur at any setting, anytime. The contributory factors and prevalent causes may vary in each reported case. Informal conversations done with some nurses revealed that medication errors commonly happen during their “busy” days, while others told the researcher that they commonly occur as a result of knowledge deficiency with certain medications and of miscommunication or misinterpretation of physician’s order. Moreover, the researcher observed that nurses in some busy hospitals are highly prone to committing medication errors. In fact, in one of these hospitals, a nurse mistakenly administered an IV drug by bolus instead of giving it at a slow rate. In another instance, a student nurse happened to give a suppository orally, not rectally instead. Still another surprising event was when a certain drug order was mistakenly read as 20 mg to be given once daily, when the drug is only available in 2 mg tablets once daily. The nurse prepared 10 tablets and gave them all to the patient. However, the error was later discovered.

And though the incidence of medication errors is kept to a minimum, it is inevitable for nurses to explore on possible effective ways to help combat such problem.

In the Philippines, the issue on medication error is one important concern that nurses are significantly paying attention to. Although oftentimes unreported or unrecognized, medication errors have become a competitive challenge of pharmacovigilance, that is, safe drug use and administration. The outcomes of low-level errors may not pose immediate harm to clients but eventually, high-level errors can result in severe complications to the client, even death. Given this, nurses are placed on the primer of prevention and management of this clinical and social problem.

With this information, the researcher was driven to look into the contributory factors and prevalent causes of medication errors as identified by nurses in Cebu City. The researcher believed that this study was worth pursuing because, in a way, the output would become an eye opener for nurses in different health care facilities. By knowing the factors and causes of medication errors, a set of recommendations can be established with the end-goal of improving client care outcomes and patient safety across all health care settings.

II. THE STUDY

Research Problem

This study determined the contributory factors and prevalent causes of medication errors among nurses in Cebu City for the period of January to December 2010 as basis for preventive measures. Specifically it sought to answer the following queries: (1) What were the contributory factors affecting medication errors among nurses in Cebu City in terms of organizational and individual; (2) What were the prevalent causes of medication errors among nurses in Cebu City in terms of preparation and administration; (3) What were the top three contributory factors and prevalent causes of

medication errors among nurses in Cebu City; (4) Was there a significant relationship between the contributory factors and prevalent causes of medication errors among nurses in Cebu City; and (5) What recommendations were proposed based on the findings of the study?

Review of Related Literature

Margolin (2010) presented a creditable, persistent determination to decrease patient harm caused by medication errors, the health care profession has recognized a number of grounds predominant in many avoidable medication inaccuracies. Systemic problems are a major factor in preventable medication errors. Systemic issues include: (1) physical factors such as poor noise, lighting, color, temperature and chaotic layout and design organization factors such as time pressure, stress, fatigue, work overload, and lack of privacy (Margolin, 2010; Chaudhury & Mahmood, 2007; Anjali, 2006); (2) errors of fatigue or distraction caused by pressure on pharmacists and pharmacy technicians (Margolin, 2010; Anderson & Townsend, 2010, National Association of Pharmacy Regulatory Authorities, 2009; Institute for Safe Medication Practices, 2009; Gianutsos, 2008); and (3) higher volume of drug preparation than can be safely performed (Margolin, 2010; Blackburn, 2010).

Some of the worst errors occur when (Margolin, 2010): (1) patient's chart is not read and interpreted well (Roy, Gupta & Srivastava, 2006; Lisby, Nielsen & Mainz, 2005); (2) professionals failed to assess clients allergies to drugs (Jones & Como, 2003); (3) drugs are administered to wrong patients (Institute for Safe Medication Practices, 2011); (4) excessive drug dosage for the patient's age, weight and condition are administered (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality, 2011); (5) handwritten orders and prescriptions by the physician may be misinterpreted by the pharmacist and nurses (Jain & Rastogi, 2009; Glabman, 2005; Hellwege, 2000; Bruner & Kasdan, 2001); (6) drugs with similar names may result in a deadly erroneous drug administration (Nordenberg, 2010; Taneja

& Wiegmann, 2004); and (7) miscommunication and misunderstanding between health care professionals is another major cause of medication errors (Rosenfield, 2009; Khowaja, Nizar, Merchant, Dias, Bustamante-Gavino & Malik, 2008; Patel, 2004).

Rosenfield (2009) stressed that doctors must take reasonable care in correctly and accurately writing prescriptions and staff must similarly confirm medication types and dosages when in doubt. In a study conducted by Lambert and colleagues (2010), audial perception experiment in spoken medication errors in the United States was undertaken to measure the influence of similarity, familiarity, background noise and other factors on health care professionals and laypersons' ability to identify spoken drug names. Objectively measurable properties of drug names were used to predict confusability, and it was found that: (1) accuracy increased significantly as the signal-to-noise ratio increased, as subjective familiarity with the name increased and as the national prescribing frequency of the name increased; (2) similarity among clinicians to other drug names reduced identification accuracy, especially when the neighboring names were frequently prescribed; (3) when names were substituted for another, the substituted name was almost always a more frequently prescribed drug.

Maurer's dissertation (2010) found that medication administration is often carried out under chaotic and stressful circumstances and is probably the highest risk activity a nurse performs – it can be minor or lead to devastating effects for the patient and also for the nurses' career. Furthermore, five topmost causes of medication errors were identified: (1) interruptions during medication pass; (2) short nurse staffing; (3) nurses caring for high acuity patients; (4) nurses working more than 12 hours in one shift; and (5) nurse knowledge of medication being administered.

In a literature review study conducted by Alanko and colleagues (2007), findings revealed that both organizational and individual factors

contributed to medication errors. Developing and improving the physical environment, error reporting, and medication management protocols were emphasized, and methods to prevent medication errors were drafted to counteract: (1) high workload, communication breakdowns, unsuitable working environment, distractions and interruptions, and similar medication products; and (2) nurses' inability to follow protocol, inadequate knowledge of medications and personal qualities of the nurse.

In the study of Mayo & Duncan (2004), several facilities depend on nurses in determining probable errors – so that they can bring them to the attention prior to its occurrence to the appropriate person. Errors were attributed to: (1) illegibility of written orders; (2) dispensing errors; (3) calculation errors; (4) monitoring errors; and (5) administration errors. These were attributed to distraction, tiredness, and exhaustion. Less than half believed that all drug errors should be reported and reasons for not reporting include: (1) fear of manager; and (2) peer reactions.

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on the Human Error theory by James Reason. This theory had been vital in the management of simple and complex errors in the healthcare delivery system. Based on the premise of this theory, humans are highly

responsible for mistakes occurring imminently in the clinical setting while at the same time providing professional care to their clients inside the facility.

Numerous notions are necessary to cognize the etiology of medication errors. Decisions taken by the authority in any institution, while well thought out and considered being correct at the time, can be unfitting and, therefore, potentiate unpredictable problems within the system. This has a direct bearing on how misfortunes develop. These can become inherent in the workplace and influence the environments in which we work and the tasks which we are carrying out. The probability of increased danger will likely occur when it creates weaknesses in the task and environmental conditions (influencing factors, but also known as contributory factors).

Individual factors were those factors which affect the performance of nurses whose actions may have an effect on the delivery of safe and effective care to patients and hence the likelihood of service delivery problem (SDP) occurring. Many factors may contribute to a single SDP. He devised a specific contributory factors framework based upon significant observation and research into the influencing and causative factors contributing to the occurrence of clinical errors. Among them are educational, personal and emotional factors.

Medication errors may lead to inexcusable

Figure 1. Human Errors in Medication Administration.

or negligent outcomes that may cause patient injury. These medication errors can occur at whatever point in a nurse's work time. Several factors have also been identified by the Philippine Colleges of Physicians (2007) as causes of medication errors. These errors may arise from doctors', nurses', pharmacists' or even patients' shortcomings. From their point of view to a nurse's responsibilities, medication may occur from causes arising through drug preparation and administration. These inevitably include those that violate most particularly the rights of medication administration. Identified causes have been significant to include those from mistaken patients, wrong calculations and dilutions, administering in one site instead of another, faulty withdrawing of liquid medicines, wrong rates, illegible physician's handwriting, confusion with drugs of similar names, and under timing or over timing medication administration. These causes have all been linked to the problems of medication errors and mismanagement.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study involved a quantitative correlational design with qualitative analysis in order to determine complementary strengths with regard to the findings of the study. The participants of the study were nurses in Cebu City: charge nurses, medication nurses, staff nurses, and nurse preceptees. These participants were chosen because they were the ones directly involved in the care of the clients admitted in the medical facility. The researcher utilized power analysis to come up with 100 nurses gathered through the use of quota sampling. Ten key informants from the pool were identified purposively for multiple individual interviews.

The study was conducted within Cebu City. The researcher conveniently utilized nurses from different public and private tertiary hospitals in the city. No particular hospital name was singled-out in this study in order to establish anonymity and confidentiality. Hence as quoted by Polit and Beck (2004):

"Anonymity is the protection of participants in a study such that even the researcher cannot link individuals with information provided".

The instrument used for this data collection was a researcher-made-multiple-response questionnaire based on the application of Human Error theory by James Reason and on findings from related literature and studies. It was validated by 3 experts and reliability was determined.

It contained a checklist of possible contributory factors and prevalent causes of medication errors. Each participant was given the questionnaire for the quantitative part. The answers acquired from the participants were then organized, collated and analyzed to generate findings. Data were processed in SPSS version 20 using the following statistical treatments: simple percentage; ranking system; and chi square with Cramer's v to determine the existence and strength of relationship of the contributory factors and prevalent causes of medication errors.

A semi-structured schedule interview guide was also prepared to gather qualitative information concerning the issue at hand. Consent was taken prior to each interview. Verbatim transcription of the audiotaped interviews was done. Recordings were then destroyed after transcriptions were rechecked. Information was indexed to convert data into smaller and more manageable units.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After a thorough collation, interpretation and analysis of data gathered, the following were the findings of this undertaking:

Profile. There were 45 staff nurses, 24 medication nurses, 17 charge nurses, and 14 volunteer nurses who were able to answer the instrument in the study. These nurses were those who work primarily in the clinical settings and who were directly in contact with their patients during medication administration and use.

Organizational Contributory Factors.

Among the organizational contributory factors of medication errors, higher workload ranked first with 86% of the responses. This is followed by communication problem and working environment both with 67% of the responses. Distraction and interruptions during medication pass garnered 53% while medication product problems had 40% of the responses. The findings implied that when nurses are assigned too many tasks to do, they tend to lose focus on proper medication preparation and administration and thus most likely could commit medication errors.

"Kung daghan kaayu ug pasyente ug trabahu-un, mawad-ankag focus ug concentration so mas prone jud ka masayup". (If we have many patients and workload, we lose focus and concentration, making us more prone to errors)

Individual Factors. For the individual factors, stress/level of tiredness came first with 78% of the responses. This is followed by inadequate medication knowledge at 67%, then inability to follow protocol with 55% of the responses. Lack of work experience garnered 42% low morale had 40% of the responses. The findings implied that medication errors commonly happens when nurses do not have enough energy and disposition to carry out all assigned tasks because of tired or stressed out with work.

"There were times when we were required to work four straight nights (graveyard shift) and it was really terrible, very tiring and stressful. You can really feel that your mind drifts. That's when your start committing errors."

"Kung kapuy, natural di jud ka katarung ug huna-huna, saputun pa jud ka". (If you're tired, naturally you can't think well, you'll even get irritated).

Drug Preparation. In terms of preparation, medication errors were greatly caused by illegible physician's order. It garnered 75% of the responses. Not at far from the first one was computing the wrong dose with 72%. Following were drug name confusion, 41%; inappropriate dilution, 38%; and drug withdrawing error, 29%. As observed, the last three causes did not attain one-half of the responses. The findings implied that it is necessary to validate and double-check physicians' medication orders to make certain that what was transcribed in the order sheet are congruent with what nurses should prepare.

"Makalagut usahay ang mga doctors, bati pag batasan, bati pajud agi. Pareha sa ilangnawng, ang ilang orders di jud masabtan."(Some doctors are irritating; their handwriting is the same as their attitude. Their orders can hardly be understood, just as how they look).

Medication Administration. For the errors arising from medication administration, the most prevalent cause was not identifying the right patient, accounting for 67% of responses. All other causes did not attain one-half of the responses. They include wrong administration time, 45%; inappropriate site, 44%; regulating at wrong rate, 42%; and interchanging routes, 35%. The findings implied that nurses should follow the fundamental rights of medication administration to prevent administering drugs to wrong clients and thus prevent unwanted events.

"There was this nurse who injected the oxytocin to the baby, instead of giving it to the mother. It was terrible, good thing, nothing happened to the baby. That was one medication error I can't forget when I was a student."

Ranked Factors. Among all factors (organizational and individual), higher workload was seen as the most contributory to medication errors. It constitutes 86% from the responses.

This is followed by stress and level of tiredness with 78% and finally communication problem and working environment with 67% of the responses.

From among the causes, illegible physician's handwriting emerged as most prevalent. It received 75% of the participant's responses. This is followed by computing the wrong dose with 72% and finally, not identifying the right patient at 67%. This made up the top three prevalent causes of medication errors among nurses.

Correlations. The following contributory factors and prevalent causes were significantly correlated with varying degrees or strength of correlations:

1. Working environment and drug name confusion (moderate);
2. Distraction/interruption and drug withdrawing error (moderate);
3. Distraction/interruption and not identifying the right patient (strong);
4. Inadequate medication knowledge and wrong adm'n. time (mod. strong);
5. Stress/level of tiredness and inappropriate site (strong);
6. Lack of work experience and drug name confusion (moderate);
7. Lack of work experience and regulating at wrong rate (moderate);
8. Low morale and inappropriate dilution (weak).

All other contributory factors and prevalent causes did not have a significant relationship with each other.

Discussion

Beginning staff nurses are nurse generalists. This means that they are expected to perform all nursing responsibilities under acceptable conditions. This implies that staff nursing is a lot broader in perspective. Meanwhile, medication and charge nursing are more specific nursing functions. As compared to the number of staff nurses, this implies that more nurses are given general assignments instead of more precise and

detailed ones. Voluntary nursing on the other hand may comprise any of the three earlier mentioned. However, in this study, less number applied for them since most of the volunteer nurses generally were not as exposed or experienced as compared to staff, medication, and charge nurses.

Shortage in RN staffing accounts most of the medication errors. Although there is surplus of unemployed RNS. It is inevitable, in fact, that some nurses give up their jobs because they are not well compensated with the burden of loads that they carry. This problem, although highly modifiable, has placed nurses in a dilemma of whether to prioritize themselves or their patients. Because once they rest, no one will care for their patients. And if they don't as well, in as much as they want to render safe care, they will really have a higher tendency to commit medication errors.

When there are too many patients to cover, the increased amount of drug administration is at risk (Margolin, 2010; Blackburn, 2010). This will eventually lead to: (1) erroneous interpretation of patient's chart, doctor's order and prescriptions (Roy, Gupta & Srivastava, 2006; Lisby, Nielsen & Mainz, 2005;); (2) inadequate drug-client-allergy assessment (Jones & Como, 2003); drugs administration to wrong patients (Institute for Safe Medication Practices, 2011); and (4) wrong drug dosage calculation based from the clients characteristics (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality, 2011).

Workload, as defined by Patterson, Cook & Render (2002), is the perception of task demands by a human agent that depends on performance criteria, task structure, task duration, and the complexity and variability of task demands, among other factors (Huey & Wickens, 1993). There are notable strategies to eliminate or reduce the adverse effects of high workloads.

Desmond, Woods & Patterson (in press) identified the following: (1) trading accuracy for speed; (2) reducing performance criteria; (3) shedding tasks; (4) deferring tasks; and (5) recruiting resources from other personnel.

When a person is bombarded with too many

stimuli, the body suffers exhaustion, and vital functions diminish. This explained why nurse who were stressed and tired but were forced to work often experience higher threats of committing medication errors. Physiologically, when a person is tired, the brain is metabolically deprived, making it function less accurately so cognition is altered and alertness is not maintained.

According to Anderson and colleagues (2006), poor communication, improper acquisition, use and monitoring of drug delivery may also lead to medication errors. Some delivery systems have inherent flaws that increase the error risk. Environmental factors that can promote medication errors include inadequate lighting, clustered and noisy work environments, and distractions during drug preparation or administration: color, temperature and chaotic layout (Margolin, 2010; Chaudhury & Mahmood, 2007; Anjali, 2006),

Medication errors can result when there is a miscommunication or misunderstanding of drug orders. These errors may be due to: (1) poor handwriting (Jain & Rastogi, 2009; Glabman, 2005; Hellwege, 2000; Nordenberg, 2000; Bruner & Kasdan, 2001); (2) confusion between drugs with similar names (Nordenberg, 2010; Taneja & Wiegmann, 2004); and (3) misuse of zeroes and decimal points, confusion of metric and other dosing units, and inappropriate abbreviations (Nordenberg, 2000). Doctors must take reasonable care in correctly and accurately writing prescriptions and staff must similarly confirm medication types and dosages when in doubt. Medication errors can also occur when doctors take an incomplete medical history from a patient. For example, the doctor might not know about the patient's allergies, any other medications the patient is taking, previous diagnoses, and lab results. Nursing homes should help treating physicians by ensuring that they provide the physician with accurate medical charts (Rosenfield, 2009).

Nurses should be especially careful when reading doctor's orders. Doctors on their part should also be responsible enough to make

written orders clear and legible. Although busy and inattentive, doctors and nurses should take a while to contemplate on their medication accountabilities and obligations. Further, there is a need for nurses to review their computation tasks before they eventually venture into medication administration. They must also be honest and open to other nurses when in doubt about written orders and dosages.

Identifying the patient ahead of medication administration should be strictly observed. The researcher believed that this is the most sensitive among all other factors and causes since it could immediately result to adverse responses by the patient. Many ways have been identified to identify the patient. The nurse is responsible for ensuring that the drug is given to the right patient. In finality, all rights of medication should always be observed.

In the end, nurses are expected to be empathetic. But where should this virtue go if a nurse erroneously administers a drug to another patient? What if the patient was his kin? This issue implied that nurses should take a moment asking the patient's name before administering medications. Prudent nurses should be accountable to their actions. The wrong patient could die with this error, hence, an alarming situation in the healthcare industry nowadays. It should be a standard operating procedure, a part of routine, an obligation to every nurse to review his patient before administering any drug or medication.

V. CONCLUSION

Based from the findings of this study, the researcher concluded that higher workload, stress/level of tiredness, communication problem, and working environment were most contributory to medication errors. Also, the researcher concluded that illegible physician's order, wrong dosage computation, and not identifying the right patient were the most prevalent causes of medication errors. Further, it was also concluded that in general, the contributory factors and prevalent causes of medication errors were not significantly

related to each other. This gave way to the notion that each of the variable was highly unique from each other and that they were greatly dispensable entities. In other words, one variable can exist even without the others. And the variables generally were independent and existential. Furthermore, as supported by James Reason in his theory, medication errors were results of human doings that may have started as “just nothing” which eventually progressed to even more serious issues or concerns. On this note, the researcher finally concluded that preventive measures should need to be imposed (or implemented) in order to prevent further patient injury by reducing the incidence of medication errors through a modification or elimination of the contributory factors and prevalent causes.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

The researcher concluded that the errors in our midst:

I. Systemic reforms: involve modifications of organizational factors

1. Staffing should be clearly and appropriately computed and planned.
2. Shifting of schedule should be done in a consistent and regular basis.
3. Ventilation, adequate lighting, and quiet environment are reinforced.
4. Open and effective communication between and among health care providers should be established and maintained.
5. Protocols should be strictly followed. An evaluation of the adherence and compliance to the protocols should be implemented and maintained.
6. Drug product labeling and packaging should be clear and protected.

II. Professional reforms: involve personal change in behavior and attitude

1. Review the “rights of medication administration”.
2. When in doubt about certain drugs, take time to ask or inquire.

3. Do not assume information, illegible orders should be clarified.
4. Adequate rest and sleep should be maintained. Take a break from work.
5. Experience is the best teacher. Learn while practicing and performing.
6. Socialization among fellow nurses should be encouraged in the unit.

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